

COST Action

Progress Report at 24 months

(03/11/2017 to 03/11/2019)

CA16204: Distant Reading for European Literary History

The Action was approved by the Committee of Senior Officials (CSO) on 23-6-2017 and has the MoU reference COST 015/17.

This report shows the data entered into e-COST to enable the Action Chair to verify the completeness and accuracy of the report with the MC prior to submitting the report via e-COST in fulfilment of the rules for COST Action Management, Monitoring and Final Assessment.

Action leadership and participants

Leadership positions

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Chair	Prof Christof Schöch	schoech@uni-trier.de +491773484840	Germany

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Vice Chair	Prof Maciej Eder	maciejeder@gmail.com +48 (12) 632-56-92	Poland

Working groups

#	WG Title	# of participants	WG Leader	Country*
1	Scholarly Resources	36	Dr Carolin Odebrecht carolin.odebrecht@hu-berlin.de	Germany
2	Methods and Tools	35	Prof Mike Kestemont mike.kestemont@ua.ac.be	Belgium
3	Literary Theory and History	33	Dr Antonija Primorac antonija.primorac@uniri.hr	Croatia
4	Dissemination	12	Dr Justin Tonra justin.tonra@nuigalway.ie	Ireland

Other key leadership positions

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
STSM Coordinator	Ms Katerina Kanellopoulou	catherine.kanellopoulou@gmail.com	Greece
Science Communication Manager	Prof Katja Mihurko Poniž	katja.mihurko.poniz@ung.si	Slovenia
GH Scientific Representative	Prof Christof Schöch	schoech@uni-trier.de	Germany

* The country displayed is:

- for the Action Chair, the country that nominated that person to the Management Committee before they were elected Action Chair;
- for the Vice Chair the country that nominated the person as a Management Committee Member,
- for all other leadership positions, if the person is a MC Member the country displayed is the country of nomination, otherwise it is the country of the person's primary work affiliation.

Participants

COST members having accepted the MoU

AT	08/05/2018	BE	26/09/2017	BA	23/08/2017	BG	12/09/2017	HR	25/09/2017
CZ	09/10/2017	DK	12/06/2018	FR	20/07/2017	DE	18/07/2017	EL	18/07/2017
HU	16/10/2017	IE	13/09/2017	IL	16/07/2017	IT	29/09/2017	LV	02/11/2017
LT	28/05/2018	MT	02/08/2017	ME	04/12/2017	NL	02/10/2017	MK	15/02/2018
NO	19/09/2017	PL	21/08/2017	PT	26/10/2017	RO	17/08/2017	RS	02/09/2017
SI	04/10/2017	ES	22/08/2017	CH	07/09/2017	UK	07/08/2017		

Other participants

Institution Name	Country
University of Newcastle	Australia
Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro	Brazil
New York University	United States
Taras Shevchenko Institute of Literature	Ukraine

Summary

The main aim and objective of the Action is to

This Action will develop the resources and methods necessary to change the way European literary history is written. Through a shared theoretical and practical framework, it will enable sophisticated computational methods of analysis of large collections of literary texts and foster insight into cross-national, large-scale evolutions across European literary traditions.

During its first two years the Action progressed the achievement of this as described below

The COST Action "Distant Reading for European Literary History" (CA16204) has made considerable progress, during the first two years of its lifetime, towards achieving the Action's main objectives. All four Working Groups of the Action have contributed to this success. In the Working Group concerned with Scholarly Resources (WG1), a theoretical and practical framework of selection criteria, encoding guidelines, data standards, validation schemas and collaborative working procedures has been agreed upon and documented. It has been implemented to create a large number of individual collections that together form the European Literary Text Collection. In the Working Group concerned with Methods and Tools (WG2), a large range of activities have been taken place to manually create reference annotations, to use them to evaluate automatic annotation tools, and to develop a strategy to integrate the annotations (tokenization, lemmatization, part-of-speech tagging, Named Entity Recognition) into the XML-TEI format of the ELTeC. In the Working Group concerned with the Literary Theory and History (WG3), the focus has been on thinking through the conceptual consequences of digital tools and methods for several key notions in literary studies, notably the novel and canonization, and on providing research scenarios and requirements for the ELTeC encoding and annotation. In the Working Group concerned with Dissemination (WG4), finally, a lot of work has gone into a large range of dissemination channels for Action activities and outputs. This has not only been important for the visibility of the Action, but has also proven to be a motivating factor for the Action participants. The Training Schools that have been jointly organized by all Working Groups as well as the Short Term Scientific Missions have been occasions to disseminate competencies in Distant Reading research and to expand and strengthen the Action's network. While a lot of work remains to be done to completely achieve the Action's main objectives, the Action has made tremendous progress on the various tasks and has achieved a high degree of visibility of the Action. The Action members have displayed an extraordinary level of dedication towards the Action's objectives and motivation to be involved in the Action's activities.

The Action will implement the following measures in the coming two years to overcome any issues identified in this report as potentially endangering the achievement of the objectives of the Action

One issue that has emerged during the last 6 months is that although we have produced a large number of novels in the ELTeC format, this work has been spread out over more collections than we initially anticipated, due to a number of factors. As a consequence, fewer collections than initially planned have now reached the status of completed collections with 100 novels. As a consequence, some of the work planned for using the collections (a) for investigations into European literary history and (b) for evaluation of key measures in Computational Literary Studies could not start as early as we had hoped. As a consequence, we plan to continue to expand ELTeC with two focus areas: (1) enable teams building ELTeC collections to reach a significant number of novels (50 at least) as soon as possible; (2) support teams working on existing, almost complete ELTeC collections (80+ novels as of November 2019) reach the status of completion (100 novels respecting the corpus composition criteria) as soon as possible. Based on this, we can then initiate and encourage research into these collections.

Action website

Achievement of MoU objectives, deliverables and additional outputs/ achievements

MoU objectives

Please self-assess and describe the level of achievement of each MoU objective. For any MoU objective that is 25% or less achieved, please add an explanation.

Mou objective	To coordinate the creation of a multilingual European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC) in three iterations.
Type of objective	1.b Coordination of information seeking, identification, collection and/or data curation 2.b Building a community around a new or emerging field of research
Level of progress	51 - 75%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>As part of this task, detailed selection and corpus composition criteria have been developed and detailed text encoding guidelines at three different levels of encoding (level 0: minimal; level 1: standard; level 2: with annotations) have been established.[1] Work on twelve different language collections has started and over 700 novels have so far been selected, encoded and published.[2]</p> <p>All collections are being created and collaboratively curated on GitHub.com in a dedicated ELTeC organization [3]. Github releases for nine collections have been published and an overall ELTeC release v.0.5.0 has been published. A copy of all releases has been placed at Zenodo.org for long-term archiving. A Zenodo “community” has been created to gather the archive copies there.[4]</p> <p>Note that we have from the start aspired to make all ELTeC data available according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). The data is Findable: Zenodo allows Harvesting with an API via OAI-PMH interface to ELTeC. It is Accessible: all ELTeC corpora are directly downloadable free of charge from a public GitHub repository [3]. The data is Interoperable: all texts are encoded at different levels of the de facto standard XML-TEI P5. The data is Reusable: All texts included in the ELTeC collection are in the public domain. The textual markup is provided with a Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0 licence (CC BY, [5]).</p> <p>A large number of Action members are involved in this task, with active corpus building teams existing in 12-15 countries. In addition, several STSMs with relevance to this objectives have taken place. Finally, each of the three Training Schools has had a multi-day track with relevance to this objective.</p> <p>See also objective #3 and deliverables #4, #5, #6 (ELTeC milestones) and #14.</p> <p>[1] https://distantreading.github.io/ [2] https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC [3] https://github.com/COST-ELTeC [4] https://zenodo.org/communities/eltec/ [5] https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/.</p>

Mou objective	To use the ELTeC to establish best practices and develop innovative methods of Distant Reading for the multiple European literary traditions.
Type of objective	1.d Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique 1.e Development of knowledge needing international coordination, pertaining to a new or improved theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
Level of progress	26 - 50%

<p>Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective</p>	<p>The focus of our work towards achieving this objective has been on the question of methods of annotation for the multilingual collections, with regard to linguistic annotation (Tokenization, Lemmatization, Part-of-speech Tagging) and Named Entity Recognition (names of people, places and organizations). A large number of samples have been selected and manually annotated as a Gold Standard for evaluation.[1] Key challenges have been to identify the best annotation methods for each language, to map results from several tools onto a shared tagset (Universal Dependencies), and to find a solution for integration of the resulting annotations into the existing XML-TEI encoded texts. This last point was a matter of close coordination with WG1, because this is relevant to level 2 (annotated texts) of the encoding guidelines.</p> <p>Beyond this work on cross-language token-based annotations, application of higher-level methods of analysis to the multilingual collections could not be started on a large scale yet, due to insufficient numbers of sufficiently large text collections (objective 1).</p> <p>Work towards this objective, coordinated by WG 2, has involved a large number of Action participants organized into several task forces. At our two large Training Schools, a dedicated multi-day track has been devoted to issues relevant to this objective. Several STSMs have taken place that are related to this objective as well. Work towards this objective has also been presented at conferences. [1] https://github.com/COST-ELTeC/WG2-Sample</p>
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<p>Mou objective</p>	<p>To engage in an investigation into the theoretical, methodological and practical consequences of Distant Reading approaches for literary history and literary theory.</p>
<p>Type of objective</p>	<p>1.a Development of a common understanding/definition of the subject matter</p> <p>1.d Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique</p>
<p>Level of progress</p>	<p>26 - 50%</p>
<p>Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective</p>	<p>We have pursued this objective with a focus on two key theoretical concepts in literary theory and literary history: the definition of the novel and the concept of canonization. Both issues are closely related not only to theory, but also to corpus building, as the definition of the novel and the formalization of the level of canonicity are key components of our text selection and corpus composition criteria, respectively. In addition, the Galway Training School (December 2018) and the Budapest Training School (September 2019) had a multi-day track that dealt with these two issues, respectively, in considerable depth.</p> <p>Action members have spent considerable time and resources on these two notions. However, with regard to more tangible outputs from these activities, we have been delayed by the complexity of the issues and the multiplicity of perspectives represented on them inside the Action, and even inside WG3. However, we now have a good strategy on how to move forward on this objective by breaking down the large objective into smaller tasks that we believe we can accomplish in the remainder of the Action.</p> <p>An important activity of WG3 in this area has been to advise WG1 and WG2, from the point of view of literary theory and history, on the research questions that are of interest to literary scholars and the kinds of information to be encoded and annotated on the texts in order to be able to answer them. These research questions have centered on enabling cross-language comparisons and evaluations of standard methods in Digital Literary Studies, on the one hand, and on questions of phenomena related to the European dimension of the history of the novel, on the other hand.</p>

<p>Mou objective</p>	<p>To foster the acquisition of state-of-the-art methods of Distant Reading, including competencies relating to data curation, standards, best practices and methods of Distant Reading analysis.</p>
<p>Type of objective</p>	<p>2.b Building a community around a new or emerging field of research</p>
<p>Level of progress</p>	<p>51 - 75%</p>

<p>Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective</p>	<p>In order to achieve this objective, we have organized several successful Training Schools targeted primarily at Early Career Investigators. These have taken place in Würzburg, Germany, in April 2018 (one track, 12 participants), in Galway, Ireland, in December 2018 (three tracks, 33 participants) and in Budapest, Hungary, in September 2019 (three tracks, 44 participants).[1]</p> <p>The first, smaller Training School has been funded with remaining funds in Grant Period 1 and has focused on digitization and text encoding. The two larger Training Schools have each featured tracks on (a) digitization, data curation and text encoding, (b) linguistic analysis and quantitative methods of text analysis and (c) concepts from literary theory and how they are affected by digitally-available data and computational methods. Each track has been implemented by one WG but the Training Schools also featured cross-cutting topics and plenary sessions.</p> <p>In addition, we have organized a workshop in the framework of a Working Group Meeting (the Lisbon meeting in February 2019), targeted not only at Early Career Investigators, but also at Working Group Members at all levels of experience. This was at a half-day workshop on the TXM text analysis software, a key software component for the Action.</p> <p>Several STSMs have also been relevant to ECIs acquiring state-of-the-art methods of Distant Reading, some related to digitization and text encoding, others to linguistic annotation and methods of analysis, others still to tool development.</p> <p>Several (though not all) of the STSMs have already been documented on the Action portal, with more to follow.[2]</p> <p>[1] https://www.distant-reading.net/events/ [2] https://www.distant-reading.net/stsm/</p>
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<p>Mou objective</p>	<p>To encourage and support the submission of competitive grant proposals both at the national and European levels.</p>
<p>Type of objective</p>	<p>2.c Bridging separate fields of science/disciplines to achieve breakthroughs that require an interdisciplinary approach</p>
<p>Level of progress</p>	<p>51 - 75%</p>
<p>Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective</p>	<p>With regard to this objective, there have been a number of successful grant proposal submissions that were in all cases closely-related to specific activities and issues in the Action and that were in most cases supported by the Action with a letter of support.</p> <p>Among these grant proposals, there has notably been a Czech “INTERCOST project; a Belgo-Polish project jointly funded by the Research Agency of Flanders (FWO) and the Polish Academy of Sciences (PAS); a project with partners in France and Romania funded by the Romanian Ministry of Research and Innovation; a multi-partner project funded in Spain; and a relatively large German project funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). For more details of these grant proposals, see the section “Additional Outputs: Proposals / Projects” in this report.</p> <p>Several further grant proposals submitted by Action members and related to the COST Action have not been successful. However, we consider this to be a normal part of submitting grant proposals and are overall very impressed by the high number of initiatives and submissions and by the level of activity in the Action regarding this objective. Further proposals are in preparation.</p>

<p>Mou objective</p>	<p>To help address the current gender imbalance among practitioners of Distant Reading research.</p>
<p>Type of objective</p>	<p>2.e Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action</p>

Level of progress	76 - 100%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>On this topic, please also see the First Progress Report which focused on this issue. The data gathered for that report showed that the gender balance in our Action is quite well overall, although the numbers are slightly less balanced for the leadership roles. This is therefore an area on which we have focused on specifically in the year since the First Progress Report. However, it is an area where relatively few occasions for change occur in the short term.</p> <p>When looking beyond MC membership and leadership roles, for example at gender balance at Action events and activities such as STSMs and Training Schools, we note that the selection criteria we have defined for STSM grantees and Training School grantees have a specific provision in favor of a gender balance in them and this clearly has effects.</p> <p>As far as Training Schools are concerned, at our Galway Training School, 19 (or 58%) of the participants have been female. As for the Budapest Training School, 22 (or 50%) of the participants have been female. Regarding STSMs, so far 9 out of 19 of STSM grantees (or 47%) have been female. While this is slightly less than half, the duration of the STSMs should also be considered. According to that metric, 172 out of a total of 320 STSM days (or 54%) can be attributed to female grantees.</p>

Deliverables

This section covers only deliverables that were foreseen for the Action, not additional outputs that were generated during the Action (these additional outputs will be added in the following section). Please select and comment on the progress with achieving each deliverable.

For deliverables that are:

- Delivered, please provide proof to enable the Action Rapporteur to confirm the delivery
- Not delivered but delivery is foreseen within 2 years please explain how the delivery will be achieved
- Not foreseen to be delivered please explain why not

Deliverable	Milestone M-0-1: "Progress Report 1" with information on the progress achieved since the start of the Action (responsibility: Management Committee).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Delivered	Month deliverable due	18
Proof of progress with achieving the deliverable	https://www.distant-reading.net/distant-reading_pr1/		

Deliverable	Milestone M-0-2: "Progress Report 2" with information on the progress of the Action since the the first progress report (responsibility: Management Committee).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	36
Explanation	The present report completes this deliverable, meaning we cannot link to it yet, but it will be completed on submission of this document.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-0-3: "Final Achievement Report" with an overview over the Action's achievements during the entire lifespan (responsibility: Management Committee).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	48
Explanation	This deliverable is an administrative deliverable and is planned for month 48 of the Action lifetime.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-1-1: The ELTeC, first iteration: subcollections for 6 languages (responsibility: Working Group 1).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	12
Explanation	We have been making considerable progress and are confident we can complete this deliverable before the end of the Action. We do not have six complete ELTeC collections at this time because we decided to work on a larger number of collections in parallel rather than focusing on a small number of collections. Work on 12 collections has been undertaken, with more than 700 novels selected and encoded (five collections with more than 80 texts, plus six collections with more than 20 texts). (Six complete collections would correspond to 600 texts.) See also deliverable #1. URL: https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/		

Deliverable	Milestone M-1-2: The ELTeC, second iteration: subcollections in at least 4 additional languages (responsibility: Working Group 1).		
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Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	24
Explanation	This deliverable has not been delivered entirely, but we have been making considerable progress and are confident we can deliver it fully before the end of the Action. We currently have more than 700 texts spread across 12 collections and need to add 350 more to reach the deliverable of a total of ten (6 plus 4) complete collections of 100 novels. See also objective #1. URL: https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/		

Deliverable	Milestone M-1-3: The ELTeC, third iteration: at least 6 expansion subcollections (responsibility: Working Group 1).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	32
Explanation	Not due until month 32. Work on several of these "expansion subcollections" is already ongoing, based on the text curation activities that have been ongoing for deliverable #4 and #5, which has helped identify texts that cannot go into the core collection of 100 novels but can be included in the extended collections. For languages where large numbers of digitized novels are available, this task is much easier than completing the first collections, which have very tight selection criteria. Preparatory work has progressed well and for French and Portuguese, work on the expansion collections has started.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-2-1: Journal paper on benchmarking and language-dependent performance evaluation of existing methods using ELTeC (responsibility: Working Group 2).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	22
Explanation	Work for this deliverable has advanced well, although it is not entirely completed. An abstract describing this work has been accepted for the DH_Budapest conference where it has been presented in September 2019. The full paper will be published in the course 2020. See: Cinková, Erjavec, Freitas, Galleron, Horváth, Ore, Smrž and Indig: "Evaluation of taggers for 19th-century fiction", Budapest_DH 2019. URL: http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/ (Programme), URL: http://elte-dh.hu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/DH_BP_2019-Abstract-Booklet.pdf (Book of Abstracts) There is another article in preparation directly related to this deliverable, to be completed in the next 6-9 months: "Resources and Tools for Sentiment Mining in Literary Corpora"		

Deliverable	Milestone M-2-2: Journal paper summarizing the results of evaluating existing Distant Reading tools and strategies for improvement (responsibility: Working Group 2).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	34
Explanation	Due in month 34. Preparatory work for this deliverable is ongoing.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-2-3: "Lessons-learned"-report about cross-linguistic use of Distant Reading Methods (responsibility: Working Group 2).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	46
Explanation	This deliverable is not due until month 46. A large amount of relevant experience has already been gained on this topic in WG1 when designing ELTeC with many different languages and literary traditions in mind. Also, a lot of relevant experience has already been gained on this issue in WG2, when designing, developing and evaluating a multi-lingual annotation pipeline for ELTeC texts. We have less experience so far directly with		

using the ELTeC texts for quantitative methods of literary text analysis because these can really only be gained once a larger number of complete ELTeC collections is available.

Deliverable	Milestone M-3-1: Journal paper outlining concepts like genre, style and authorship in computational and non-computational literary history (responsibility: Working Group 3).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	15
Explanation	This deliverable has not yet been completed in the framework of the Action, in part because it turned out to be overly ambitious as one single paper, and progress on this got delayed as a consequence. We now plan to publish this content in a different format, namely in the form of several shorter and more focused posts on a research blog, most likely in the Action's own "News" section or in a different, suitable venue.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-3-2: Journal paper outlining different approaches to literary periodization and canonization in relation to literary history and Distant Reading (responsibility: Working Group 3).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	28
Explanation	This deliverable is due in month 28 (February 2020), but will most likely be delayed by several months. Also, the paper will focus on canonization alone, which has turned out to be a crucial issue in the Action. The Budapest Training School in September 2019 has been the occasion for several Action members to investigate this issue, with one track being focused on canonization and several Action members involved in teaching this track. An outline, a strategy for writing this paper, and assignment of Action members to research and writing tasks are there and work is progressing.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-3-3: Journal paper on theoretical assumptions and foundations of Distant Reading research (responsibility: Working Group 3).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	42
Explanation	This deliverable is not due until month 42. A paper proposal directly related to this topic has been submitted to the international Digital Humanities conference in Ottawa (DH2020) as a first step. We plan to extend the ideas formulated there into a more formal publication in the course of 2020.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-4-1: Guidelines for a dissemination strategy, supporting the other WGs and the MC (responsibility: Working Group 4).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Delivered	Month deliverable due	4
Proof of progress with achieving the deliverable	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465809		

Deliverable	Milestone 4-4-2: The Action's portal is functional and online, ready to host the ELTeC (responsibility: Working Group 4).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Delivered	Month deliverable due	6
Proof of progress with	https://distant-reading.net		

achieving the deliverable

Deliverable	Milestone M-4-3: The Final Action Dissemination materials are available (responsibility: Working Group 4).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	46
Explanation	This deliverable is not due until month 46 in September 2021 and depends on our activities and achievements until then. As a consequence, work has not started on this report beyond general planning.		

Additional outputs / achievements

Co-authored Action publications

Please enter below ONLY publications (including publications that are submitted but not yet accepted):

- that are on the topic of the Action, and
- that are co-authored by at least two Action participants from two countries participating in the Action, and
- for which the Action networking was necessary.

Please pay special attention to representatives of Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) in each publication. If there are more than 20 publications you *may* choose to enter only the most 20 significant (in terms of Inclusiveness, Excellence and the MoU Objectives).

	Bibliographic data	Countries participating in the Action among authors	Open Access	COST cited?	COST funds?	Relevance to H2020 Societal challenge	Peer Reviewed?
1	<p>doi:10.5281/zenodo.1297690</p> <p>Christof Schöch, Maciej Eder, Carolin Odebrecht, Mike Kestemont, Antonija Primorac, Justin Tonra: "Distant Reading for European Literary History. A COST Action". In: Digital Humanities Conference 2018: Book of Abstracts. Mexico City: ADHO, 2018. URL: https://dh2018.adho.org/distant-reading-for-european-literary-history-a-cost-action/ (peer-reviewed abstract; poster)</p>	BE, HR, DE, IE, PL	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
2	<p>doi:10.5281/zenodo.3546325</p> <p>Carolin Odebrecht, Lou Burnard, Borja Navarro Colorado, Maciej Eder, Christof Schöch: "The European Literary Text Collection ELTeC". Digital Humanities Conference 2019: Book of Abstracts. Utrecht: ADHO, 2019.</p>	DE, PL, ES, UK	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
3	<p>Carolin Odebrecht, Lou Burnard, Borja Navarro-Colorado (with all WG1 members): <i>ELTeC Guidelines. Web-accessible versions of discussion documents</i>. URL: https://distantreading.github.io/ (Contains "Sampling Criteria for the ELTeC", "Encoding Guidelines for the ELTeC", "Workflow proposal" as well as further documents that, taken together, form the conceptual and practical basis for the creation of ELTeC (objective #1 and deliverable #4).</p>	DE, ES, UK	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	N

4	doi:10.5281/zenodo.3552488	DE, UK	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
	Lou Burnard, Christof Schöch and Carolin Odebrecht: "In Search of Comity: TEI for Distant Reading". What is text, really? TEI and beyond. Book of Abstracts. Graz: ZiM, 2019. https://graz-2019.tei-c.org/program/book-of-abstracts/						

Projects resulting from Action activities

Please enter below all the projects on the topic of the Action resulting from Action activities, involving at least one Action participant, and for which the Action networking was necessary.

The Action reported 6 project(s) and 3 proposal(s) resulting from the Action networking.

Key details of the projects are shown below.

#	Title	Countries participating in the Action among proposers	Main proposer name	Funder	Amount	Call identifier	Relevance to H2020 Societal Challenge
1	Modeling of Complexity in Literary Texts	CZ	Silvie Cinkova	National	186500 €	Interexcellence-Intercost, ID LTC180320	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
2	Zeta and Company. Measures of Distinctiveness for Computational Literary Studies	DE	Christof Schöch	National	467950 €	DFG, SPP 2270, ID 424211690	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
3	Hajduk Novels in Romania During the Long Nineteenth Century: Digital Edition and Corpus Analysis Assisted by Computational Tools	FR, RO	Roxana Patras	National	15000 €	PN-III-P3-3.1-P M-RO-FR-2019	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
4	Romane românești pentru Distant Reading – ELTeC: digitizare, procesare conform standardelor TEI-xml și	RO	Roxana Patras	National	5000 €	PNCDI III 2015-2020, P1:	Europe in a changing world,

	validare					Dezvoltarea sistemului național cercetare dezvoltare, Subprogramul 1.1. Resurse umane, Proiecte de Mobilitate pentru cercetători 2019	inclusive innovative and reflective societies
5	Gender and Spiritism in Nineteenth-century Andalusia (1840-1920): Gendered Networks and Borderlands / Género y espiritismo en Andalucía (1840-1920): enfoque filológico y traductológico	HR, ES	Rosario Arias	National	23979 €	UMA18-FEDER JA-167	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
6	Deep Learning in Computational Stylistics	BE, PL	Mike Kestemont	Trans-national	25000 €	FWO/PAS	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies

Other outputs / achievements

Please enter below any additional outputs/ achievements on the topic of the Action that contribute to the COST mission: “COST enables break-through scientific developments leading to new concepts and products and thereby contributes to strengthen Europe’s research and innovation capacities”, and for which the Action networking was necessary (e.g. a patent, standards, white paper).

Output / achievement description	Dependence of achievement on the Action networking
Series of videos with statements by several Action participants explaining their perspective on "Distant Reading".	High
Journal article (single author): Luiza Marinescu (2019): "From Close to Distant Reading of 100 Romanian Novels". In: Studia ubb Philologia LXIV.2, 239-250, DOI: https://doi.org/10.24193/subbphilol.2019.2.19	Medium
Journal article (single author): Borja Navarro-Colorado (2018): "On Poetic Topic Modeling: Extracting Themes and Motifs From a Corpus of Spanish Poetry", in: Frontiers in Digital Humanities 5:15, DOI: https://doi.org/10.3389/fdigh.2018.00015	Low

Conference paper: Silvie Cinková, Tomaž Erjavec, Cláudia Freitas, Ioana Galleron, Péter Horváth, Christian-Emil Ore, Pavel Smrž and Balázs Indig: "Evaluation of taggers for 19th-century fiction", Budapest_DH 2019. URL: http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/ (Programme) URL: http://elte-dh.hu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/DH_BP_2019-Abstract-Booklet.pdf (Book of Abstracts)	High
Conference paper: Isabel Araújo Branco, Diana Santos, Paulo Silva Pereira and Raquel Amaro: "A ação COST e o que representa e representou para a leitura distante em português / The COST action and what it represents and represented for distant reading in Portuguese". First Workshop on Distant Reading in Portuguese. Oslo: University of Oslo, 27-28 October 2019.	High
Conference paper: Primorac, Antonija. 2019. "Infrastructural Challenges for Large Scale Digital Text Corpora: A View From the European Margins." presented at the Humanities, Arts and Culture Data Summit and DARIAH Beyond Europe workshop, National Library of Australia, Canberra, March 28. https://www.humanities.org.au/special-event-1903/ .	Medium
Talk: Christof Schöch, „Distant Reading for European Literary History: A COST Action“, <i>DARIAH Text and Data Analysis Working Group Meeting, DARIAH Annual Event 2018</i> , Paris, 22.-24.5.2018. http://dariah-tda.github.io/meeting/activity/workshop/2018/05/11/WG-Meeting-Paris-2018.html	Medium
Talk: Christof Schöch, „The COST Action Distant Reading for European Literary History“, UA-DAAD Exchange Meeting, org. Hugh Craig, Newcastle University, March 21, 2018.	High
Keynote: Christof Schöch, „Repeating and Repeatable: Distant Reading between Past and Future“, <i>DH_Budapest 2019</i> , Budapest, September 25-27, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/conf2019/	High
Journal article: Arias, Rosario y Juan-José Martín-González. "Distant Reading vs. Close Reading: Las nuevas tecnologías y la crítica literaria". <i>Las Humanidades en el mundo digital / El mundo digital en las Humanidades</i> . Valencia: Tirant, 2019. 342-49.	High
Conference paper: Cvetana Krstev, Jelena Jačimović, Branislava Šandrih and Ranka Stanković: "Analysis of the first Serbian literature corpus of the late 19th and early 20th century with the TXM platform". DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	High
Conference paper: Ranka Stankovic, Diana Santos, Francesca Frontini, Tomaž Erjavec and Carmen Brando: "Named entity recognition for distant reading in several european literatures. DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	High
Conference paper: Silvie Cinková, Tomaž Erjavec, Cláudia Freitas, Ioana Galleron, Péter Horváth, Christian-Emil Ore, Pavel Smrž and Balázs Indig: "Evaluation of taggers for 19th-century fiction." DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	High
Conference paper: Silvie Cinková and Jan Rybicki: "Stylometry in literary translation via universal dependencies: finally breaking the language barrier?" DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	Medium
Conference paper submission: Herrmann, J. Berenike; Odebrecht, Carolin; Santos, Diana; Francois, Pieter: "Towards Modeling the European Novel. Introducing ELTeC for Multilingual and Pluricultural Distant Reading", Digital Humanities Conference 2020.	High
Conference paper submission: Ore, Christian-Emil; Herrmann, Berenike; Odebrecht, Carolin; Santos, Diana: "ELTeC: A comparable corpus of novels in many European literatures", Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 2020 (DHN2020).	High

Impacts

Please describe the impacts (the short- to long-term scientific, technological, and / or socioeconomic changes produced by a COST Action, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended) that have resulted, or might result, from the Action in the following table (one impact per line).

Description of the impact, i.e. what will change, and for whom, as a result of what the Action achieved	Type of impact	Timing of impact
Action members have gained considerable experience with the challenges involved in collaboratively building a large-scale, multilingual textual resource and have documented our strategy to deal with these challenges in a detailed manner through the white papers on selection criteria and corpus composition as well as on Text Encoding Principles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
All Action contacts, of which there are close to 200 across all categories (regular MC members, substitute MC members, trainers, trainees, STSM grantees) have become part of our international network.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
Through the different grant proposals submitted by Action members in the context of the Action, the proposers have in some cases gained freedom from other tasks to do more research related to the Action and to their research interests, and in some cases been able to hire researchers and form teams that allow them to achieve more progress with their research. (This impact has been achieved in several cases and we hope to add several more cases until and beyond the end of the Action.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
Action members have obtained, so far and in total, around 723,429 EUR in third-party funding through Action-related grant proposals. (This impact has already been achieved and we expect to see several more proposals, including at least one large one, until the end of the Action and immediately after it ends.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
Computational analyses of the ELTeC collections will have an impact on the way European literary history is studied and understood. This impact will start to be felt towards the end of the Action and hopefully continue well-beyond the end of the Action.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Foreseen within two years of the end of the Action
The availability of ELTeC will enable (a) comparative research into the history of the European novel and (b) cross-language evaluation studies of computational methods for literary text analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Foreseen by the end of the Action
The collaboration of corpus linguistics, computational linguists, computational literary scholars and literary historians will strongly contribute to increase the exchanges and collaboration between these distinct, but in fact connected, fields. This is already the case inside the Action but will expand beyond the Action over the coming years.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Foreseen by the end of the Action
The best practices we have established in the Action with regard to corpus building (corpus composition criteria, encoding principles, integrated annotation, collaborative curation and open access publication) are highly likely to have the impact we hope for, that is, to serve as a showcase and a best practice example well beyond the Action.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Foreseen by the end of the Action

Please describe how the Action is advancing the careers, skills and network of researchers, including ECIs (for example: joint supervision of graduate and PhD students, research exchanges not funded by the Action, collaborations, Training Schools with ECTS accreditation, joint projects and jobs prospects).

The Action is clearly advancing the careers, skills and network of researchers, notably of course through the activities

and meetings of the Working Groups and in the context of the Training Schools. Through additional funding obtained in several collaborative grant proposals, researchers are taking part in research exchanges not funded by the Action, for example between Poland and Belgium or between Romania and France. The international network of many researchers is clearly strengthened considerably through the Action. The career benefits we describe here concern Early Career Investigators (up to 8 years after the Ph.D.) as well as more established researchers (more than 8 years after the Ph.D.).

The career benefits are mainly to researchers with the following amount of experience after their PhD: ≤ 8 years.

Which of the stakeholders described in the “Plan for involving the most relevant stakeholders” in the Action’s MoU have been engaged and how? What additional stakeholders have been, or will be, engaged and how?

Individual researchers and teams in the fields of Corpus Linguistics, Computational Linguistics, Computational Literary Studies and Literary History have already been engaged with as Action participants. Early Career Researchers are well-represented in the Action, both in leadership positions, as regular or substitute MC members, or as trainees and STSM grantees. (So far, we have had 90 trainees and 18 STSM grantees.) We have engaged with national or regional libraries, for example in the process of obtaining digital facsimiles of relevant novels in their holdings, or when working to obtain relevant metadata. We will do more in this area once we can showcase ELTeC and research that is using it.

Dissemination and exploitation of Action results (other than co-authored Action publications listed previously)

Please describe the Action's dissemination and exploitation approach as well as all activities undertaken to ensure dissemination and exploitation of the Action results and the effectiveness of these activities.

Dissemination and exploitation approach of the Action

The Action's dissemination and exploitation approach relies on a multi-pronged strategy that aims to reach a wide range of target groups. Specific measures include a series of videos on Distant Reading, posters for conferences that have in each case been submitted to multiple conferences, an actively-maintained Twitter account and an actively-maintained presence on Facebook.

Dissemination

Dissemination meetings funded by the Action

Title of Dissemination meeting	Meeting date	Meeting country	Action participant	Event name and hyperlink to the website	Title of presentation	Description of added value to the Action
N/A						

Other dissemination activities

E.g. participation to non-Action meetings, e.g. EU Parliament, meetings with policy makers, experts in the field, regional authorities.

Item/activity	Target audience	Outcome	Hyperlink
WG4 members are collectively running a Twitter account for the Distant Reading COST Action.	Researchers and students in the Humanities, Social Sciences, Computer Science and professionals in the Library world with an affinity for digitization and digital research methods.	We have more than 550 followers on Twitter as of November 2019. Our tweets typically receive 2000 "impressions" (views), many receive 5000, and some even receive more than 8000 impressions.	https://twitter.com/DistantReading
Publication of the "Distant Reading Recommends" series of blog posts.	Researchers in literary scholars and people more informally interested in literary history across Europe. In "Distant Reading Recommends", an Action member introduces a novel, published between	So far, we have been able to publish five blog posts in the "Distant Reading Recommends" series, written by scholars and concerning novels from Lithuania, Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia and Slovenia.	https://www.distant-reading.net/category/distant-reading-recommends/

	1850 and 1920, from one of the participating countries in our Action. These novels may be important or notable within the individual nation's literary tradition, but less well-known in the broader European context. By bringing these novels to light, we aim to further advance our objectives of creating a broader, more inclusive, and better-grounded account of European literary history and cultural identity.	We have reason to believe that the "Distant Reading Recommends" series has already garnered considerable attention. We plan to continue with blog posts in this series during the lifetime of the Action. One indicator if this are the number of "impressions" we see from the tweets promoting these posts on Twitter.	
Publication of the "Distant Reading Talks" series of video statements on Distant Reading.	Scholars in Literary Studies, Digital Humanities, Computational Linguistics and Computer Science.	The videos provide personal, scholarly perspectives on the issue of Distant Reading.	https://www.distant-reading.net/videos/
Creation and curation of a Zenodo community for "Distant Reading for European Literary History".	Scholars in Literary Studies, Digital Humanities, Computational Linguistics, Computational Literary Studies, Computer Science.	This Zenodo community makes various documents that we archive on Zenodo more visible as an ensemble. As such, it increases the visibility and findability of our outputs.	https://zenodo.org/communities/distant-reading/
Creation and curation of a Zenodo community for "European Literary Text Collection" (ELTeC)	Scholars in Literary Studies, Computational Literary Studies, Computational Linguistics, Digital Humanities, and Computer Science.	This collection unites all archive copies of the ELTeC collections in one place. In this way, it increases the visibility and findability of our ELTeC collections.	https://zenodo.org/communities/eltec/
The First Workshop on "Distant Reading in Portuguese" was organized on 27-28 October 2019 at the University of Oslo	Students, Early Career Investigators and other Scholars in Portuguese Linguistics and Literary Studies.	The workshop was successful in bringing the issue of Distant Reading into the local community of Portuguese Linguistics and Literary Studies.	https://translate.google.com/translate?sl=pt&tl=en&u=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.hf.uio.no%2Filos%2Fforskning%2Faktuelt%2Farrangementer%2Fgjesteforelesninger-seminarer%2F2019%2Fencontro-sobre-leitura-distante-em-portugues.html
Christof Schöch gave an interview to the SWR Radio Station.	The target audience of this activity is the general educated public.	This activity is likely to have brought considerable attention to the Action's key objectives.	https://www.uni-trier.de/fileadmin/fb2/LDV/DH/digital-humanities.wav
Newspaper article about the Action: "Die europäische Literaturgeschichte wird neu geschrieben. Digital Humanities an Uni Trier bereiten Literatur neu auf"	The target audience of this dissemination activity is the general public in Germany.	This activity resulted in increased visibility of the Action's objectives in a local context. The article has been republished in several venues with high visibility in Germany, e.g. at IDW -- https://idw-online.de/de/news701449 -- and at KOWI -- https://www.kooperation-international.de/	https://www.wochenspiegelive.de/trier/stadt-trier/artikel/die-europaeische-literaturgeschichte-wird-neu-geschrieben-53978/

		aktuelles/nachrichten/detail/info/digital-humanities-weltweites-netzwerk-erforscht-europaeische-literaturgeschichte/ .	
Action members are actively using a Facebook account for the Action.	The target audience of this activity is a broader audience of students and researchers in the Humanities.	So far, since the creation of the account in October 2019, almost 200 people already follow the Facebook account.	https://www.facebook.com/distantreading
The Action liaises actively with the Special Interest Group on "Digital Literary Stylistics" (SIG-DLS) within the Alliance of Digital Humanities Associations (ADHO).	Fellow researchers in Computational Literary Studies at the international level across Europe but notably beyond Europe.	The reach of our online dissemination efforts is expanded through the SIG-DLS network.	https://dls.hypotheses.org/168
We have added information about the Action to the project directory run by the European Association for Digital Humanities (EADH).	The target audience of this activity is fellow researchers in Digital Humanities broadly conceived across Europe.	The visibility of the Action has been enhanced by our presence on the EADH project directory.	https://eadh.org/projects/distant-reading-european-literary-history
Action member Justin Tonra has published an online magazine article on "What is distant reading?"	The publication venue, RTÉ Brainstorm Ireland, has researchers across the Natural Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities as well as the general public interested in research as its target audience.	This article has produced a high level of visibility for the Action on the one hand, and for the more general issue of computational methods in the humanities, on the other hand.	https://www.rte.ie/brainstorm/2019/1114/1090846-what-is-distant-reading/
Action members have written an English-language Wikipedia article about "Distant Reading". This article will also be translated into several other European languages by Action members.	The target audience of this dissemination activity is the general, interested public.	An explanation of the key term in the name of our COST Action is now available on one of the most visited websites in the world.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distant_reading
At least one Action member has used ELTeC texts in their teaching: MA students in the 'Introduction to Digital Humanities' module have used novels from ELTeC for the purposes of completing an assignment on computational analysis of an unknown novel.	The target audience of this exploitation activity have been MA students in the "Digital Culture" programme at NUI Galway, Ireland.	The MA students have used authentic texts to gain experience with digital methods of analysis for literary texts.	http://www.nuigalway.ie/courses/taught-postgraduate-courses/digital-cultures.html
Several Action participants from Basel (CH) -- Simon Gabay, Berenike Herrmann, Simone Rebora -- have been organizing a training school on "Distant Reading – Tools and Methods" to take place in December 2019.	The target audience of this activity are primarily early career investigators in Literary Studies and Linguistics from Swiss universities.	The participants will acquire competencies in the areas of digitization using Optical Character Recognition, corpus design, text encoding and metadata management as well as analytical approaches to text collections.	https://www.unil.ch/doc-digitalstudies/home/menuinst/activites-du-programme/distant-reading-tools-and-methods.html

Exploitation activities

Please describe below any activities undertaken to ensure exploitation (use, in particular in a commercial context) of the Action's achievements.

Item/activity	Target audience	Outcome
We are in the process of building a conversion process that will allow us to transform the hundreds of novels contained in the ELTeC collections to EPUB for reading on ebook readers and we will publish these novels for reading on major, free, international ebook platforms.	The general public interested in reading famous novels as well as in discovering forgotten novels from across Europe in their original language.	Expected result: High level of visibility of our Action outside strictly academic circles, and new readership for the novels we have published.

Other matters

This section is confidential to the Management Committee, the Action Rapporteur and the COST Association, and is not included in the version of the report that is published on the COST website.

COST Members with pending intention to accept the MoU

The following COST Members have the status “intention to accept the MoU”: SK. Please comment.

The MC vote on the application of Slovakia becoming a participating country in our Action has resulted in a unanimous approval of the application. We are looking forward to working with the Slovak team.

Difficulties in implementing the Action

If any difficulties are experienced in the implementation of the Action (e.g. imbalances of participation across the Working Groups, inactive country representatives) please describe these below. Please also describe the efforts made by the MC to address these.

One minor, general concern is that the regular MC members are not always the most active Action participants, while very active Action participants are sometimes substitute MC members only. When issuing invitations for participation in MC meetings, this can lead to delays in the issuing of invitations to the substitute members, when regular MC members do not decline their invitation in a timely manner. This is being addressed in two ways: first, through an early start of the invitation process and second, through requests directed at MC members to consider passing their regular MC member status to other Action members, when they find it hard to devote much time to the Action.

Endangerment Measures

Taking into account the issues identified throughout this report, please summarise the measures the Action will implement in the coming two years to overcome any issues identified as potentially endangering the achievement of the objectives of the Action.

One issue that has emerged during the last 6 months is that although we have produced a large number of novels in the ELTeC format, this work has been spread out over more collections than we initially anticipated, due to a number of factors. As a consequence, fewer collections than initially planned have now reached the status of completed collections with 100 novels. As a consequence, some of the work planned for using the collections (a) for investigations into European literary history and (b) for evaluation of key measures in Computational Literary Studies could not start as early as we had hoped. As a consequence, we plan to continue to expand ELTeC with two focus areas: (1) enable teams building ELTeC collections to reach a significant number of novels (50 at least) as soon as possible; (2) support teams working on existing, almost complete ELTeC collections (80+ novels as of November 2019) reach the status of completion (100 novels respecting the corpus composition criteria) as soon as possible. Based on this, we can then initiate and encourage research into these collections.

Suggestions for improvements to COST framework/ procedures

The mandate of the Scientific Committee includes providing advice to the COST Committee of Senior Officials on possible improvements to the COST framework. Please describe below any improvements that you believe should be made to the COST framework.

We appreciate the fundamental idea that COST Actions are intended to provide funding for networking activities, training opportunities and coordination of research, rather than for research itself. However, in many situations it would be highly beneficial to be able to award small amounts of funding to Action participants: for example, in order for them

to purchase a software licence they need to work more efficiently, to cover digitization fees in order to make specific primary sources available; or to pay student helpers for some hours of work supporting a given Action deliverable. Even if this was limited to a small percentage of a Grant Period budget (for example, 5% maximum), this would often make a big difference, especially for Integration Target Countries where it can be challenging to raise even such smaller funds.

Sustaining the network beyond the Action

Are there any plans to sustain the network beyond the end of the Action?

YES

Please describe how the network will be sustained beyond the end of the Action.

We are developing several ideas for EU-level grant proposals to sustain the network beyond the Action. We have identified several relevant funding programmes: (1) the Horizon 2020 "European Research Infrastructures" programme with the "INFRAIA-02-2020: Integrating Activities for Starting Communities" call; (2) the Horizon 2020 "Europe in a changing world" programme with the "DT-TRANSFORMATIONS-12-2018-2020: Curation of digital assets and advanced digitisation" call; (3) The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Initial training Network (ITN) programme. At the moment, we are focusing on the first of these programmes and are building a network of proposers that reaches beyond the Action.

Emerging topics/ developments in the field of the Action

Please describe any emerging topics or potentially important future developments identified during the Action and that could potentially be addressed by future COST activities such as Actions S&T Conferences or Exploratory Workshops.

The Action has already been, in the first two years, a tremendous learning experience and experimental laboratory for many of our ideas with regard to Distant Reading methods used to investigate European Literary History in an innovative, reflective, computational manner. However, it has also become clear that many of the principles, ideas, best practices and resources (both corpora and tools for analysis) will benefit immensely from being scaled-up considerably, using dedicated financial resources at a much larger scale than what is possible in the framework of the Action. We are convinced that the issue of cross-linguistic corpora, resources, tools and methods is an emerging, key challenge for research into the languages, literatures and cultures of Europe and would be very keen on giving visibility to these issues in the framework of COST activities.

Annex 1: Types of objectives

1 - Coordination of scientific and technological activities at a European level

- 1.a - Development of a common understanding/definition of the subject matter
- 1.b - Coordination of information seeking, identification, collection and/or data curation
- 1.c - Coordination of experimentation or testing
- 1.d - Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
- 1.e - Development of knowledge needing international coordination, pertaining to a new or improved theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
- 1.f - Achievement of a specific tangible output that cannot be achieved without international coordination (e.g. due to practical issues such as database availability, language barriers, availability of infrastructure or know-how, etc.)
- 1.g - Input to stakeholders (e.g. standardization body, policy-makers, regulators, users), excluding commercial applications
- 1.h - Input for future market applications (including cooperation with private enterprises)
- 1.i - Dissemination of research results to the general public
- 1.j - Dissemination of research results to stakeholders (excluding specific input in view of knowledge application)

2 - Community building

- 2.a - Building a community around a topic of scientific and/or socio-economic relevance, allowing for knowledge exchange and the development of a joint research agenda
- 2.b - Building a community around a new or emerging field of research
- 2.c - Bridging separate fields of science/disciplines to achieve breakthroughs that require an interdisciplinary approach
- 2.d - Acting as a stakeholder platform or trans-national practice community, pertaining to a certain area of socio-economical or societal application, or to a certain market sector
- 2.e - Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action

Annex 2: Dimensions of successes

1 - Breakthroughs

- 1.a - Scientific breakthrough
- 1.b - Technological breakthrough
- 1.c - Breakthrough in socio-economic or societal applications

2 - Policy contribution

- 2.a - Contribution to regulatory policy
- 2.b - Contribution to environmental, infrastructural or agricultural policy
- 2.c - Contribution to economic or socio-economic policy
- 2.d - Contribution to social, cultural or legal policy

3 - Capacity building

- 3.a - Building capacity in an existing field of science and technology
- 3.b - Building capacity in bridging separate fields of science and technology
- 3.c - Building capacity in a new or emerging field of science and technology
- 3.d - Building capacity in valorising and implementing advances and applications in science and technology
- 3.e - Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action